
Digital Marketing Strategies of Vivo for the Disabled Community: E-Waste Management, Accessible Features, and Applications

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ABSTRACT: This research aims to explore vivo's sustainable marketing strategy that focuses on inclusivity and e-waste management. Using a qualitative approach, data was collected through in-depth interviews with influencers and content analysis of vivo Indonesia's Instagram. The results showed that vivo's marketing strategy involving collaboration with influencers is effective in building brand image. However, challenges in e-waste management and inclusivity still need attention. Key recommendations include educating audiences about e-waste management through the 'Trade-in for Tomorrow' program and the production of recycled phones. In addition, vivo is advised to offer products that are friendly to people with disabilities, such as Talkback and Inverse Color features for visually impaired users. The implementation of this strategy is expected to increase sales and strengthen vivo's image as a company that cares about the environment and inclusivity. A sustainable marketing strategy that includes education on e-waste and increased product inclusiveness will make a positive contribution to the environment and society, while strengthening vivo's position in the market.

KEYWORDS: Disability; vivo; E-waste; Features

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the key elements of success in marketing strategies, according to Haque-Fawzi (2022), is customer satisfaction. Marketing is closely tied to business promotion, emphasizing that addressing consumer needs is a fundamental economic and social requirement for a company's sustainability. The core pillars of the marketing concept include target market focus, meeting customer needs, integrated marketing, and profitability. Furthermore, the customer-centric approach highlights the importance of gaining a larger share of customers' spending by fostering loyalty and focusing on customer lifetime value (Yansaharita et al., 2023).

Marketing strategies serve as a guideline to prioritize objectives, policies, and rules that direct a company's marketing efforts over time at all levels. These strategies aim to allocate resources effectively in response to environmental and competitive dynamics. A key goal of marketing strategies is to define targets for predetermined segments, ensuring organized product promotion to achieve optimal results (Yansaharita et al., 2023).

Marketing strategies serve as guidelines to prioritize objectives, policies, and regulations that direct a company's marketing efforts over time, at every level, and with specific references and allocations. These strategies primarily respond to environmental and competitive dynamics. The goal of marketing strategies is to define targets for each predetermined segment, ensuring that product marketing is more organized and yields optimal results in line with expectations (Yansaharita et al., 2023).

The information society era, as highlighted by Waters (1966), underscores the importance of information access for all societal layers, including the disabled community. In this context, effective access to information through technology becomes crucial. This capability empowers the disabled community to dominate markets, adapt to social dynamics, and actively participate in an increasingly advanced and complex society, aligning with the demands of modern times (Mutia, 2023).

The integration of knowledge and innovation, supported by systematic and organized technological growth, has become a key factor in shaping the information society. In today's era, society does not solely rely on the availability of technology but also on the ability of its members to optimally access information across various aspects of life (Mutia, 2023).

One product category that has been aggressively promoted in recent years is smartphones. Since 2016, smartphone ownership has experienced a significant increase, replacing feature phones, which previously dominated the market. According to a 2017 Nielsen survey conducted across 11 major cities in Indonesia, 67% of the population owned mobile devices, with 44% being smartphone users. In contrast, only 26% of this population continued to use feature phones (Nisa, 2019).

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This data reflects a significant shift in consumer preferences toward more advanced and multifunctional technology offered by smartphones, compared to the limitations of feature phones. This increase did not happen by chance but was driven by several key factors, including intensive and sustained advertising campaigns by smartphone manufacturers. Through various media channels, these advertisements successfully captured consumer attention by highlighting advanced features such as high-speed internet access, a wide range of applications, and high-quality cameras available on smartphones (Nisa, 2019).

Furthermore, continuous technological innovation by smartphone manufacturers has played a significant role in the surge in popularity. Every year, smartphone producers compete to introduce new features that increasingly attract consumer interest, ranging from improved app performance and more elegant designs to increasingly sophisticated AI capabilities. The combination of effective marketing strategies and rapid technological advancements has been the primary driver behind the shift in consumer preferences from feature phones to smartphones in recent years. This trend not only demonstrates consumer adaptation to new technology but also reflects the increasingly competitive market dynamics where innovation is key to survival and growth (Nisa, 2019).

Unfortunately, alongside the rapid increase in smartphone and other electronic device usage, there is a major downside that is often overlooked: the potential for an uncontrolled rise in electronic waste (e-waste). This issue has become increasingly severe in Indonesia, where challenges in managing e-waste have yet to receive adequate attention from various parties, including the government, industry, and society. One of the primary causes of this problem is the absence of specific regulations explicitly governing electronic waste and its distribution. Without a clear legal framework, managing e-waste becomes highly challenging and poorly coordinated.

As a result, electronic waste continues to accumulate, posing significant negative impacts on the environment and public health. Hazardous materials contained in e-waste, such as heavy metals and toxic chemicals, can leach into soil and water, threatening ecosystems and the health of exposed individuals. Additionally, the lack of adequate infrastructure to support e-waste management serves as a major barrier. Existing recycling and electronic waste processing facilities are still very limited, causing much of the e-waste to end up in landfills or even being illegally incinerated, further worsening environmental conditions (Purbasari et al., 2022).

Technological knowledge is undeniably important, as almost all activities today are made easier through the use of technology. With technology continually evolving, it is imperative to update this knowledge on an ongoing basis. Technological literacy has now become a standard in the professional world, which underscores the aim of this discussion to examine technology trends as a guide for future developments. This discourse aspires to inspire efforts to enhance societal welfare and reduce disparities, including those experienced by individuals with disabilities, by optimizing strategies for e-waste management, device features, and applications to improve accessibility and inclusivity. Thus, effective e-waste management and continuously updated technological knowledge can work hand in hand to create a more prosperous and inclusive society.

The leading Android smartphone brand vivo offers features tailored to every generation globally. Established in Dongguan, Guangzhou, China, in 2009 under vivo Communication Ltd., it operates as a subsidiary of the major telecommunications company BBK Electronics. From its inception, vivo has focused on innovation and product development to meet the demands of a dynamic global market. By understanding diverse consumer preferences, vivo has successfully developed smartphones that are not only technically advanced but also designed to provide an optimal user experience.

vivo positions itself as a brand that combines elegant aesthetic design with cutting-edge technology, making it particularly popular among young consumers who prioritize both style and functionality. vivo's portfolio includes smartphones, accessories, software systems, and both online and offline services across the globe.

In August 2014, under the banner of PT. vivo Mobile Indonesia, vivo began entering the Indonesian market with an initial focus on the low-end segment (SES C and B). The market's initial response to vivo was lukewarm, partly because the brand was also associated with unrelated products like Power Banks (portable batteries for charging electronic devices, a real scenario in Indonesia), while the market was dominated by competitors such as OPPO, Samsung, and Xiaomi. Additionally, the presence of various products under the "vivo" name, such as vivo condoms and vivo energy (a fuel station brand), created confusion among consumers regarding brand identity.

In the highly competitive Indonesian smartphone industry, vivo Mobile Indonesia had to adopt a strategic focus, especially in managing integrated marketing communications through social media and online platforms. Despite the challenges, vivo Mobile Indonesia has built a strong loyal audience amidst the fierce competition in the Android market and the rapid growth of technological trends. By maintaining a clear and consistent strategy across its social media and online platforms, vivo has strengthened its position and expanded its reach to diverse and unique audiences. This approach not only enhances brand loyalty but also drives long-term success in the Indonesian market.

As of 2024, vivo remains highly active in promoting its brand on social media platforms: Instagram (@vivo_indonesia) with 949,000 followers, TikTok (@vivo_indonesia) with 1.4 million followers, Facebook (@vivo) with 28 million followers, and X (formerly Twitter) (@vivo_indonesia) with 65,000 followers. These platforms are synchronized to deliver consistent content,

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focusing primarily on product promotions and high-definition imagery that reflect the Unique Selling Point (USP) of their products, smartphones with superior camera features.

The accessibility needs of individuals with disabilities encompass several critical aspects. First, there is a need for training on how to use accessibility features available on smartphones, as many visually impaired individuals express interest in utilizing these features when adequately trained. Second, raising awareness about how smartphones can facilitate independent daily living activities is essential, as a lack of awareness poses a significant barrier to access. Third, collaboration between vision rehabilitation professionals, computer scientists, and individuals with visual impairments is crucial in designing assistive mobile technologies that are innovative, acceptable, and adaptable. Lastly, proper training is vital for the productive and consistent use of smartphones, particularly in employing screen readers and other accessibility applications (Senjam et al., 2021).

Persons with disabilities often face low-income levels or unemployment (Maroto & Pettinicchio, 2022). This is supported by various studies indicating that educational attainment significantly influences the ability to master technology in an online environment. In reality, the primary cause of the disability gap lies in barriers to technology usage, as current technological advancements tend to favor non-disabled individuals while presenting challenges for those with disabilities. In other words, disability-friendly technologies are still scarce. This condition is largely due to a lack of awareness and concern regarding the needs of persons with disabilities (Mutia, 2023).

II. METHODOLOGY

This method adopts the theory of inclusive design, utilizing a collaborative approach that combines empirical research and theory-based design. The aim is to develop interventions that not only address practical problems but also contribute theoretical insights that can be utilized by other researchers. This process involves researchers acting as agents of change and participants serving as collaborators (Restianty et al., 2024). Within the context of inclusive design theory, this approach focuses on creating solutions accessible to individuals of varying abilities, minimizing barriers, and maximizing inclusivity (Al Haddar, 2023; Restianty et al., 2024).

The type of research approach employed in this study is descriptive research using qualitative data methods. Aristawidia (2018) explains that descriptive research aims to describe and address issues related to phenomena occurring in the present through the collection of information from targeted subjects. The qualitative data approach involves gathering information or data through a deductive reasoning process, which is then verified and tested before drawing conclusions as a source of data.

Data collection in this study is conducted through interviews with research subjects. The collected data pertains to user experiences related to e-waste management and the role of persons with disabilities. The subjects involved are individuals with disabilities who have experience using electronic devices. This study aims to involve these subjects to refine Vivo Indonesia's marketing strategies, helping individuals with disabilities optimize their activities using technology.

III. RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

1. E-Waste Management with Disabilities

The Ministry of Environment (2024) notes that the growing dependence on electronic devices in the digital age drives the demand for ever-newer gadgets, which in turn increases the amount of electronic waste (e-waste). This behavior aligns with the provisions of the Second Amendment to the 1945 Constitution, particularly Article 28H, which emphasizes the right of citizens to a good and healthy environment. Article 28H, paragraph (1) of the 1945 Constitution stipulates that everyone has the right to a good and healthy environment as part of the right to a decent life. This article stresses that the state has the obligation to ensure that every citizen can enjoy an environment that is not only clean but also supports health and well-being. The increasing dependence on electronic devices, which leads to the accumulation of e-waste, could threaten this right if the waste is not managed properly.

Electronic waste is a rapidly growing type of waste containing various toxic substances, such as heavy metals, which can pose significant health risks and environmental impacts if not properly managed. The Global E-Waste Statistics Partnership (GESp) in 2020 estimated that in 2019, the global production of electronic waste reached 53.6 million metric tons, and this figure is projected to rise to 74.7 million tons by 2030. E-waste contains hazardous materials such as lead, mercury, and cadmium, which can threaten human health and ecosystems. The toxic components in e-waste can contaminate soil and water, with health impacts such as respiratory disorders, skin diseases, and neurological damage. Inadequate management of electronic waste could exacerbate this situation, consistent with GESp's findings that show a significant rise in global e-waste.

The phenomenon related to e-waste management and community activities has been thoroughly studied by AD (2023), who found several interesting findings in Kuningan Regency. The research shows that the level of public awareness about the importance of household e-waste management is still low. Many residents tend to throw away e-waste with regular household trash without considering the potential environmental impacts. This is due to a lack of knowledge about the dangers of e-waste and the proper management methods (AD, et al., 2023).

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Moreover, AD (2023) also revealed that infrastructure for e-waste management in Kuningan Regency is still very limited. There is no organized electronic waste collection system at the household level, so unused electronic devices are often left to accumulate in homes or sold to third parties without going through proper processing according to standards. The lack of recycling facilities and special disposal sites for e-waste is a major obstacle to electronic waste management in the region.

The importance of waste management education must be emphasized so that the community can understand and apply sustainable waste management principles. Outreach programs facilitate everyone in enhancing human resource capacity (HR) to understand and implement sustainable waste management concepts. With this increased capacity, it is hoped that disability group managers can be more independent in managing waste in their environments, thereby providing a positive impact on the environment and the welfare of the group members (Sukamdani, 2022).

Teaching in this program is crucial and should be conducted by instructors with experience in waste management and community empowerment. These instructors are responsible for delivering materials on the importance of proper waste management, effective waste processing methods, and strategies for raising environmental awareness among the community, especially disability group members. The teaching approach used is participatory, where disability group managers are encouraged to actively participate in every training session so that they can practically apply the knowledge they gain (Sukamdani, 2022).

The outreach in the environmental conservation education program includes various aspects, from introducing the basics of waste management, such as sorting organic and inorganic waste, to composting and recycling techniques that can be done at home. In addition, participants are also taught the importance of maintaining environmental cleanliness and how proper waste management can support the health and well-being of the community. This outreach also includes discussions on the challenges faced in waste management and practical solutions that can be implemented by disability group managers (Sukamdani, 2022).

With the application of waste management education, the community becomes more aware of their role as agents of change in the environmental community, promoting better waste management practices, and contributing to environmental conservation efforts. This program also aims to strengthen solidarity among disability group members through activities that support mutual interests while improving their quality of life through a cleaner and healthier environment (Sukamdani, 2022).

Recycled phone production under the Vivo brand could become an important part of this sustainable marketing strategy. By promoting recycled phones on a large scale, Vivo can highlight its efforts to reduce environmental impact through the use of recycled materials. This aligns with the growing public awareness of environmental issues (Putri, et al., 2023). Implementing this strategy will help Vivo strengthen its brand image as a company concerned about the environment.

According to an interview with Lydia Putri, HR Manager at the Vivo factory in Tangerang, this shows Vivo's commitment to sustainability through long-term monitoring and electronic waste management in collaboration with external partners. However, the lack of disclosure about certain partnerships raises concerns. Transparent communication regarding e-waste management and collaboration with Environmental Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) could enhance Vivo's public image and align sustainability goals. The author found that Vivo releases more than 10 new phone models annually in Indonesia.

2. Vivo's Accessibility Features and Inclusive Design

Vivo's smartphone features must also include adaptive and supportive designs for everyone, including individuals with disabilities. According to Herbawan & Sharif (2023), the design of accessible smartphones creates a positive purchasing intention. This technological adaptation encourages Vivo to offer features like Talkback and Inverse Colour for visually impaired users. However, these features are underutilized in Vivo's marketing strategy because they believe that such features are also available on other Android phone models. Highlighting and improving accessibility features, as competitors such as Samsung and Apple have done, could expand Vivo's appeal to a broader audience.

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In addition to the need for supporting designs, the role of brand ambassadors becomes crucial for promoting a product. Choosing a brand ambassador with a disability also holds significant potential in changing public perceptions. A disability brand ambassador can symbolize courage and equality (Ullyya et al., 2022). Through this approach, the company can demonstrate that the rights of individuals with disabilities are equal to others, especially in the context of using female representations, which are often featured in advertisements. This equality can also help break societal stigmas about the limitations of people with disabilities in public spaces (Ullyya et al., 2022).

The role of female disability icons has become increasingly visible in media distribution. One example is the advertisement by Wardah, a well-known beauty brand in Indonesia. In the ad, Wardah features a female disability model, providing a worthy and

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inspiring representation. This not only changes public perceptions about beauty and capability but also encourages the recognition of the rights of individuals with disabilities in various sectors of life. This role is a significant step toward inclusivity and the recognition of disability rights in multiple fields (Rahakbauw & Salakory, 2018).

The appearance of a female disability model in the Wardah ad radiates strong confidence despite physical limitations. Generally, individuals with disabilities often feel insecure due to their physical conditions. However, the ad highlights facial expressions and appearances that show physical shortcomings are not obstacles to confidence. As Mirhan & Kurnia (2016) have noted, confidence is a crucial element in developing a positive self-image, aligning with the brand image. Confidence not only strengthens an individual's positive image but also increases the brand's attractiveness to its targeted audience.

This confident attitude not only enhances individual branding but also presents a significant market opportunity for Vivo in creating inclusive product designs. This would not only contribute to the company's positive image but also position Vivo as a leader in providing technology that empowers everyone, including people with disabilities, to feel confident and independent in their daily lives.

Sustainable and Accessible Marketing Strategy

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Putri (2023) emphasizes the importance of integrating sustainability into long-term business strategies by identifying four approaches: social, economic, and environmental. On the other hand, the trend of organizational adoption (between doubt and reluctance) towards green marketing orientation for sustainability can increase risks and losses if businesses fail to implement sustainable practices. Green marketing strategies, which consist of a set of tools and marketing elements, allow companies to serve their target markets and achieve organizational goals without harming the natural environment (Putri et al., 2023).

Based on this framework, Putri (2022) highlights how mobile phone manufacturers are increasingly adopting environmentally friendly practices by incorporating recycled materials into their products. This approach not only reduces environmental impact but also aligns with growing consumer demand for sustainable products. These organizations prioritize customer satisfaction and strive to build a positive reputation among them. To achieve this, marketers apply strategies that benefit both customers and the environment. Companies can also enhance their brand image and attract environmentally conscious consumers (Putri et al., 2022). One crucial issue to address in today's era is electronic waste, where transparent education about its environmental impact is essential. Through the 'Trade-in for Tomorrow, vivo for Future' program, vivo users can exchange their old phones and accessories for new products from vivo. This initiative not only supports collaborative efforts in reducing electronic waste but also has the potential to increase the company's sales. Furthermore, vivo could consider developing a line of phones made from recycled materials, branded with the vivo recycling trademark, and promoted extensively to raise awareness and engage consumers.

Lister (2023) ensures that accessible marketing means ensuring technology features that can be seen, heard, used, and understood by as many people as possible. As a technology company, vivo must target people with disabilities by offering products such as Braille manuals, interactive voice assistants, an improved TalkBack system, and specialized earphones for the hearing impaired. This special edition could be launched by collaborating with Putri Ariani (IG @arianismaputri).

Putri Ariani is an ideal candidate to serve as a brand ambassador for vivo, particularly in representing the disability community. As a visually impaired singer, Putri has proven that physical limitations are not an obstacle to achieving extraordinary success. Since a young age, Putri has demonstrated her exceptional talent in the music world, with achievements that inspire many. One of her most prominent accomplishments was winning "Indonesia's Got Talent 2014," where her vocal talent was recognized by a wide audience.

Her success on the international stage further solidified her reputation, especially when she received the Golden Buzzer and placed fourth on "America's Got Talent 2023." This recognition not only highlights Putri's talent but also provides a platform for people with disabilities to perform and be recognized globally. Putri's involvement in the music industry continues as she collaborates with both national and international artists. Her consistent dedication makes Putri an inspiring young figure and a strong representative for the disability community in the entertainment industry. Her role as a brand ambassador for vivo would send a powerful message about inclusivity and empowerment, while also strengthening the brand image of caring for diversity and the uniqueness of each individual.

Putri Ariani's Instagram account has gained 1.9 million followers, indicating that she has built a large and diverse fan base. Her followers are not only drawn to her musical talent but also deeply appreciate the inspiring values she represents, especially through her courage and resilience in facing various challenges. This large following is a strong indicator of Putri's significant influence on social media, making her a highly potential candidate for the brand ambassador role, given her ability to effectively reach and influence a broad and diverse audience.

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Putri Ariani has the potential to be a celebrity-influencer through her Instagram account. This classification refers to well-known individuals such as actors, singers, or athletes who have gained popularity through the media and have a large following on platforms like Instagram, Facebook, and YouTube (Jayasinghe, 2021). There are several categories of influencers identified by Campbell and Farrell, including celebrity influencers, mega-influencers, macro-influencers, micro-influencers, and nano-influencers. The key difference between these categories is the number of followers, with celebrity influencers often having more than a million followers.

The benefits of using celebrity influencers in social media strategies include increased exposure and brand reach, as they often have a very large following. Moreover, celebrity influencers can influence consumer purchasing decisions, with 80% of consumers reportedly making purchases after receiving recommendations from an influencer. Their usage also enhances brand trust and awareness, as the content they produce tends to be more engaging, gaining public reputation, and their followers' trust in both the influencer and the brand (Jayasinghe, 2021).

Putri Ariani's social media, particularly Instagram, often serves as a platform for netizens to react positively to her posts. These reactions are full of praise and support, consistently affirming that Putri is not only admired but also respected for her humility and extraordinary dedication. This positive sentiment further strengthens her position as an ideal figure to represent a brand like vivo in campaigns focused on inclusivity and empowering women with disabilities.

Meanwhile, vivo has a significant following with more than 900 thousand followers on Instagram (@vivo_indonesia). Globally, vivo also boasts a large following, including over 25 million followers on Facebook. As one of the leading brands in Indonesia, vivo features several prominent figures as brand ambassadors, including international and local celebrities such as Agnes Monica, Maudy Ayunda, and JKT48. Globally, vivo has partnered with famous actors like Chris Wu and sports celebrities like Virat Kohli.

In Instagram content, vivo is also involved in various environmental initiatives. One of these is the program to reduce the company's carbon footprint by designing environmentally friendly products and packaging. vivo believes that economic growth must go hand in hand with environmental sustainability. By utilizing an environmentally friendly design evaluation system, vivo assesses the environmental impact of the entire product lifecycle and strives to minimize that impact as much as possible. Vivo continues to improve the use of high-performance, environmentally friendly materials that reduce resource and energy consumption, minimize pollution, and enhance recyclability or biodegradability of every product.

The selection of Putri Ariani as a brand ambassador for vivo Indonesia is considered very significant with vivo's new Instagram strategy. By using Instagram as the primary platform, vivo can leverage Putri Ariani's influence to increase brand visibility and awareness among a wider and more diverse audience. Campaigns focusing on accessibility technology and inclusivity can be highlighted through feed posts, stories, and reels, strengthening vivo's message of sustainability and social responsibility. Putri Ariani's involvement also has a substantial following, which can increase interaction with vivo's content and reinforce the brand's image as a supporter of diversity and accessibility.

Individuals with disabilities have the opportunity to capitalize on existing trends in their capacity as brand ambassadors for well-known products. They can highlight their uniqueness and the diversity of their work. Furthermore, they can collaborate with companies that are committed to inclusivity principles and broader representation in their advertising campaigns. However, it is crucial for these individuals to selectively choose brands that genuinely support inclusivity and not just use diversity as a marketing strategy (Houston & Haller, 2022).

The image that people with disabilities must portray in order to represent a brand's positive image is one that demonstrates strength, independence, and capability. People with disabilities need to be shown as individuals who not only face challenges but also achieve and contribute significantly to society. They should be portrayed as equals to non-disabled individuals, with abilities and potential that are not limited by their physical or mental conditions. This image not only promotes inclusivity but also challenges stereotypes that often portray people with disabilities as weak or dependent (Houston & Haller, 2022).

Furthermore, people with disabilities must be represented in contexts that show their uniqueness as consumers and users of products. They should be depicted as integral parts of the target audience, with the same preferences, needs, and aspirations as other consumers. By doing so, including people with disabilities in advertisements can enhance a brand's image as an inclusive, innovative, and socially responsible entity. Products that successfully portray people with disabilities in a positive light can gain greater consumer trust and strengthen customer loyalty through inclusive and empathetic values (Houston & Haller, 2022).

This approach may carry risks in the public's reception of recycled products compared to new ones, with long preparation related to R&D, intellectual property rights, distribution, and electronic waste management and collaboration. Meanwhile, the risks in special editions for disabilities may result in high development costs for specific functions and market strategies with low ROI. Additionally, a miscommunication strategy on online media can cause misunderstandings in the market.

In the development of smartphone-based assistive technologies for people with disabilities, particularly those with visual impairments, expected accessibility features must include various capabilities that improve their interaction with devices. One essential feature is the screen reader (such as VoiceOver on iPhones or TalkBack on Android), which allows users to hear verbal descriptions of content displayed on the screen. Additionally, features like magnification or zoom, as well as high contrast display

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modes, are crucial as they allow text and visual elements to be enlarged, facilitating reading. Support for Braille displays that can be connected to devices is also an important feature, as it enables visually impaired users to read digital content through the Braille system, giving them greater access to digital information (Senjam et al., 2021).

Special applications designed to assist visually impaired users also play a significant role in improving accessibility. Some popular apps include Be My Eyes, which connects users with volunteers to assist with visual tasks, and Seeing AI from Microsoft, which uses artificial intelligence to describe the user's surroundings, read text, and recognize faces. Apps like Aira provide real-time visual assistance through video calls controlled by trained agents. Specialized navigation apps like BlindSquare or Google Maps with enhanced accessibility features are also very helpful in supporting user mobility (Senjam et al., 2021).

Although many features and applications have been designed to assist people.

IV. METHODOLOGY

This study emphasizes the importance of sustainable marketing strategies to strengthen the vivo brand image, both online and offline. One of the key strategies recommended is educating the audience about electronic waste management through the 'Trade-in for Tomorrow' program and the production of recycled phones. This program allows users to exchange their old phones and accessories for new vivo products while supporting a collaborative electronic waste management campaign. This step not only has the potential to increase vivo's sales but also demonstrates the company's commitment to environmental sustainability.

Through a marketing strategy focused on inclusivity, vivo can create a broader positive impact. This strategy will not only help vivo attract more consumers from the disability community but also strengthen the company's image as a brand that cares about inclusivity and social sustainability. By raising awareness and improving accessibility for people with disabilities, vivo contributes to the creation of a more just and equitable society. On the other hand, this approach can also boost sales, as more inclusive products are likely to attract a larger customer base. In the long run, this commitment to inclusivity and social sustainability will enhance customer loyalty and vivo's brand image in the public eye.

Vivo's strategy of appointing Putri Ariani as a brand ambassador is a strong first step in expanding the inclusivity image of its products for people with disabilities and promoting environmental sustainability through electronic waste recycling. By choosing Putri Ariani, a disabled musician and influencer, vivo not only reinforces the positive message of equality but also demonstrates real support for the empowerment of individuals with disabilities. This can increase the brand's appeal among consumers who value diversity and inclusivity, while also opening up opportunities for vivo to reach a wider audience.

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